

SOCIAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN AZERBAIJAN AND COMPARISON WITH WORLD COUNTRIES

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Abstract

Tourism plays a special role in the economic life of Azerbaijan. In connection with the development of Tourism, first of all, the export and import of the tourism product is growing. The flow of foreign capital into the country is ensured. For this reason, every year there is work related to the development of tourism in the country. The State Tourism Development Program for 2010-2014 was adopted in Azerbaijan. Hospitality is a direction of development of industrial tourism. Therefore, every year local and foreign companies in the country invest in this field.

Also, the reputation of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the international world is increasing along with its economic and political development. This, in turn, leads to an increase in business trips and capital investments. The popularization of the country, social status has a direct impact on Business Tourism and investment. Elements such as the holding of special competitions and meetings within the country, the introduction of cultural centers, etc., are of particular importance.

The main factor that ensures the formation of the hospitality industry is the arrival and accommodation of tourists in the country. There are sharp differences between the number of tourists arriving and leaving the country every year.

The international networks of the hospitality industry continue to grow every year. International hotels in Azerbaijan also influence the development of hotels through investments. Strong representatives of the hospitality industry in the tourism market ensure the development of global networks of the hospitality industry by entering the tourism market of Azerbaijan. In the regulation of the hospitality industry, the cost of living, the number of newly built hospitality establishments, the level of quality in hotels, the level of development prospects of the respective enterprises of the budget hospitality industry, etc., factors play a key role.

Keywords: hospitality industry, tourism market, hotel, investment, international experience.

Introduction

International self-regulation, the development of the hospitality industry network and the steps taken in this field give encourage progress in this area in our country. Thus, the methods used by well-known companies are applied by bringing them to the country.

The international development of the hospitality industry has accelerated in the 21st century. Thus, 90% of the hospitality industry in the USA and 40% of industrial enterprises in European countries work in a network system. The role of several world-famous personalities in the formation and development of the hospitality industry network is great. These are Elsvot, Statler. Examples include Isidore Sharp, Caesar Ritz, Willard Marriott, Conrad Hilton, and William Kemmons, who laid the foundation for the hospitality industry chains that are popular in our time. Through your experience, the hospitality industry they built grows every year and continues to play a leading role in our time.

These rich experiences applied in the hospitality industry are applied in the hospitality industry of Azerbaijan (5, p.217).

Currently, designers prefer to build modern 5-star hospitality facilities. The main reason for this, in their opinion, is that in the hospitality industry costs are returned faster and higher returns are obtained. Now, many brands work in hotel chains and other hotels in Azerbaijan. Due to the economic crisis in recent years,

there have been setbacks in the development of the hotel business industry. Since this industry is associated with many industries, this has affected their development.

Nowadays, the main hospitality industry in Azerbaijan, such as Ramada, Hilton Baku, Holiday Inn, Park Inn, Radisson, Marriott, etc., serves customers. However, not every citizen can benefit from a quality hospitality industry. First of all, the reason is the price factor. The quality hospitality industry is primarily influenced by its pricing policy. This is due to the fact that the formation of reputation covers a long period, and funds are constantly allocated for its protection. This is very essential and important. At the same time, most of the cost of services falls on the share of cash. In recent years, travel abroad has led to an increase in the number of citizens and a decrease in the number of tourists coming to the country due to the slow development of the hospitality industry in the country. Citizens of the country go on vacation abroad, which leads to the outflow of capital from the country. It is also local tourism.

This is due to the high cost and low quality of the services of firms. Entrepreneurs operating in the tourism sector in the territory of Azerbaijan pay more attention to tourists from the middle class. In this regard, 3 and 4 stars are preferred in the hospitality sector. In the branded hospitality industry, there is no way for the average tourist to relax, so they go to places

that fit their budget. These are 3 and 4 star hospitality establishments.

The state of the hospitality industry in Turkey

Many countries focusing on tourism development adopt concepts to attract tourists to this area. The role of neighboring countries in the hospitality industry of Azerbaijan is great. One of these countries is Turkey. According to research carried out by EVA Real Estate, it ranks 4th in Europe and 6th in the world.

The hospitality industry in Turkey, which is developing as a tourist destination, should focus on sound investments with the right policy. According to the research, the number of 3- and 4-star hotels was organized in parallel. On the other hand, special importance is given to investment related to the development of alternative types of tourism - boutique and concept hotels.

Cansel and Turgut Yazici, director of EVA Real Estate, noted that a study was conducted on the development of tourism in Turkey, and noted that numbers play a special role in the hospitality industry. According to him, the income of the European Hospitality industry is the basis of tourism income in the countries.

The main reasons for the development of tourism in Turkey are low prices and quality of service. In recent years, terrorist attacks are coming to the country. This led to a decrease in the number of tourists. It should be noted that as a result of intense competition in Azerbaijan, it is especially important to apply the methods used in Turkish tourism to local enterprises. Also, the normalization of the price factor in the hospitality industry, improving quality, marina, health, sports, as well as golf tourism in Turkey can have positive results in the development of Azerbaijan. Georgia is one of the neighboring countries of Azerbaijan, which is developing in the field of Tourism every year. In 2016, the number of foreign tourists visiting Georgia increased significantly compared to previous years. 3,400,335 tourists visited Georgia in January-June 2016. These data increased by 10.6% compared to January-June 2015. The number of tourists coming to Georgia is 15% from Azerbaijan, 1.5% from Turkey, 10.3% from Russia, 24% from Russia. The number of tourists from Ukraine and Iran increased by 82%. According to the statistics of 2015, Georgia's income from tourism amounted to 1.94 million dollars [4, p.44]. The cost of a bus tour to Batumi, Georgia varies between 150 to 160. The cost of transportation of the tour includes 3 meals a day.

Buses from Azerbaijan to Batumi depart from Ganja. If you look at the prices, you can see that it is very cheap compared to Azerbaijan. We see both foreign tourists and those who do not want to relax in the country, since there are no affordable prices in our country or in neighboring countries. Double rooms in some hotels in Azerbaijan cost 60 AZN including breakfast. But in Georgia, this price is 60 manats cheaper than a 5-day service. The number of hospitality establishments established in beautiful places of Azerbaijan is much more. But the price factor causes the number of customers to decrease. Examples of such recreation centers are Nabran, Guba, Gabala, etc. Now, if we are talking about the devaluation process in the

field of tourism, then increasing the number of tourists coming to Azerbaijan and ensuring capital flow to the country will have a positive effect in a number of areas. In Azerbaijan, tourists spend less in dollars than they pay in manats.

Another reason why the hospitality industry of Azerbaijan is lagging behind is its inability to fully create a competitive environment.

While the potential in the south of the country was sufficient, the infrastructure in the north of the country was weak and the condition of the roads led to the dominance of Tourism. Compared to the income of the population, the prices are very expensive. Therefore, there is competition in the country and in this environment.

Concepts aimed at increasing investments in this area should be developed and such a policy should be implemented.

The hospitality industry in Europe

France is one of the leading countries in the hospitality industry. France is considered the cradle of tourism. 83 million tourists come to the country every year.

A large number of tourists in France leads to an assessment of the quality of the hospitality industry. Each of the hospitality establishments in France has its own design and architectural style.

The most used hospitality industry in the country is Balmoral, Hotel de Sezo, Hotel de Notre Dame, Shangri-La Hotel Paris, Hotel Galileo, Hotel Chateau Frontenac, Chess, etc.

Many hospitality industries in France, services such as airport delivery, internet, room service, bar, restaurant, suites, special desks for disabled, sports and health center etc. are offered. At the same time, a large number of people live in small 2- and 3-star hotels.

Another country where the hospitality industry is developing is Great Britain. In the UK, there are rules that make it easier to book hotel rooms. Hence, the hospitality industry lists rooms on many relevant websites and makes online bookings. Thus, customers have the opportunity to book a room in advance for their personal use. This should increase the benefit-completeness ratio (11, p.89).

It should be noted that this system is used not only in the UK, but also in France, Italy, Greece, the USA, Turkey and Germany, as well as in countries operating in the tourism sector. Also, since 2011, a wide selection of 57 order systems has been created, conditions have been created for its implementation in Azerbaijan. Many tourists who want to visit the country prefer to use the country's booking services. The mentioned countries have developed in the hospitality industry and ensured the development of this industry. Azerbaijan also refers to the management function, service level, local hospitality industry of such countries.

In another case, foreign investors invested in the country under large brand names, and hospitality industry networks were opened. The development of the hospitality industry in our country, which is a part of such a network system, has good prospects in time. The management system of the foreign hospitality industry and European hospitality, its use in enterprises leads to the

improvement of quality. The following are the names of such hospitality industry networks.

An example can be given. Kempinski Hotel Badamdar, which is part of the Kempinski network, was opened in Baku in June 2011. The European service style is used in the hospitality industry.

The Kempinski hotel chain is considered the oldest network in the hospitality industry. This is the history of the hospitality industry. It dates back to 1862. However, the hospitality industry began in 1897. The worldwide Kempinski Hospitality Industry network includes more than 65 hospitality industries in 24 countries. Independent hospitality industry Kempinski is one of the creative members of the World Hotel Association. Kempinski was built in Azerbaijan. The hospitality industry in Badamdar is distinguished by its level of service and architectural style. Azerbaijani architectural traditions are used in the construction of the hotel. The Fairmont hospitality industry first opened in 1907 in San Francisco.

Most overnights in the industry are seniors. It is used by the president, the disabled and ministers (9, p. 67).

A luxurious hospitality industry is being built in the Mountain Park of Azerbaijan. There is this beautiful and amazing view of Baku from the hospitality industry. It was possible to organize a high level of service in the hospitality industry created by foreign investors. So, the hotel has 58 wheelchairs and nannies for children. The hotel's business center is open 24/7.

Founded in 1937 by Ernest Henderson and Roberts Moore, the Sheraton Hotel & In 1947, the New York Resort Foundation managed to take the 5th place in the chain hospitality industry list. Rapidly growing, Sheraton Hospitality had 100 industry-owned hotels in the United States in 1961. Ernest Henderson's efforts helped the Sheraton hospitality chain achieve the expected results. Therefore, he has able to buy and sell hotels at a low price. At Henderson's death, the number of Sheraton hospitality industry representatives reached 154. Sheraton Hotel operates at Heydar Aliyev International Airport in Baku. The hospitality industry, called the Airport Hotel, is designed for businessmen, tourists, transit passengers and is at the service of tourists. All hotels are equipped with internet, TV, air conditioning, dishes. At the same time, the rooms are serviced 24 hours a day. It serves 207 standard, junior, executive and resident rooms in this large hospitality industry. Restaurants catering to the high end of the hospitality industry, such as Flavors, Silk-Way, cater to guests.

The hospitality industry offers services in European, Asian and American styles. On the other side there is a separate outdoor barbecue area.

The hospitality industry also has a tea and coffee corner. Coffee Viana offers a variety of sweets.

In addition, the hotel has an entertainment and recreation area - "Fly Inn", sports and fitness rooms, and a sauna for guests. Hyatt, a hotel chain operating in Azerbaijan, was founded by Jay Pritzker.

In 1954, an agreement was signed between Jay Pritzker and Hyatt Woy Dane and the hospitality industry was renamed Hyatt.

In 1957, the first Hyatt hotel complex was opened. Ten years later, in 1967, with the opening of the Hyatt Regency Atlanta hotel in Atlanta, United States, the hospitality industry gained worldwide recognition. The hospitality industry, famous for its unusual design style, soon began to attract tourists, appearing in front of them. The hospitality industry's grand hall, glass elevators, and revolving restaurants also served customers. For the first time, Hyatt hotels were opened abroad in 1969. The hospitality industry in Hong Kong is Hyatt's international debut. Then hospitality hotels are opened in various cities in the Philippines, Mexico, Singapore, Taiwan and Australia.

Currently, there are 250 Hyatt hotel businesses worldwide. England in 1990, Hyatt hospitality industry opened in 1991, Indonesia in 1998 and Germany in 1998. Hyatt's headquartered is located in Chicago, USA, and is called the Pritsker Family Hyatt Center in Chicago. The Hyatt hospitality industry is built around the environment. A link is established between hotel design and environment. There are several types of Hyatt Hospitality Network:

1. Hyatt Regency Hotels – Hyatt is a 5-star business center of the hospitality industry chain that operates mainly on the streets.

2. Grand Hyatt hotels - built in the city center and have a large number of rooms. In addition to modern technologies, ancient hospitality traditions are used in the hospitality industry.

3. Park Hyatt Hotels is a hospitality industry based on high-quality European-style small luxury rooms. The level of service and professionalism of the personnel in these hotels is higher. There are two types of service in the hospitality industry: custom and personalized. There are such hotels in Tokyo, Japan and USA.

4. Hyatt Resorts - built in beautiful scenic locations. The hotel has special gyms and entertainment centers.

5. Andaz - has been operating since April 2007. The name means "personal style". The hotel provides special services. Among the 60 most beautiful hotels. The first such hospitality industries opened in London, Texas and New York.

6. Hyatt Summerfield Suites is a type of hospitality industry. Designed for a long stay. The rooms are equipped with kitchen utensils.

7. Hyatt Place - known for its high quality and service, this hospitality industry is more suitable for business travelers. The main reason behind the division of Hyatt Hospitality industry is to provide better service to the customers and therefore to ensure development according to hospitality industry standards.

The hospitality industry is expanding its range of activities from year to year, taking into account the needs of customers, new strategic plans.

The hotel serves its regular customers decorated with fruits, champagne and flowers. The company closes its offices once a year, and managers work together with ordinary employees. This is part of Hyatt's strategic plan. So, the management gets acquainted with the work-related problems. This in turn prevents some problems. One of the successful steps taken by Hyatt is to create an effective management system.

Managers develop new concepts every year. The main purpose of this is to study the wishes and desires of customers, to satisfy them and to satisfy all needs at a high level. Thus, managers offer new services to guests. This Hyatt Management system applies to all hotels in the hospitality industry. Hyatt prefers to take into account the wishes of customers. For the first time, the company presented the Hyatt business plan to business guests. This plan welcomes business guests. The rooms are equipped with technical equipment such as fax, printer, computer. For families, the hospitality industry offers the Camp Hyatt program. Separate rooms have been set up for teaching and playing the children of family guests. Staffing is part of Hyatt's successful policy. Special attention is paid to the selection, training, education, placement of the company's leaders, placement in the right areas, management and improvement of relations between the personnel in accordance with the given instructions. It is also positive for the development of the hospitality industry network. The first hospitality industry Hyatt was opened on May 19, 1995 in Baku. The hospitality industry consists of 160 rooms - 124 Gwin, 21 Twin, 8 Junior, 6 Executive, 1 President.

All rooms have TV, air conditioner, mini bar, telephone, bathroom. The Park Hyatt hotel, part of the Hyatt chain of companies, was opened in Baku in 1999. The hospitality industry consists of 159 rooms. For example, Hyatt International Center, Hyatt Tower, Hyatt Recency, owned by Hyatt.

Our city has a hospitality industry. It played an important role in the formation of the global business of the hospitality industry (2., p89).

Conrad Hilton has done many important things in the hospitality industry. Because the banker Conrad Hilton had a good relationship.

The first Hilton hospitality industry opened in 1925 in Dallas. Soon, in the international business of the hospitality industry, Conrad Hilton begins to open hotels abroad. In 1953, he opened his first hotel in Europe in Madrid, Spain.

The main reason for Hilton's success is its good experience in the hospitality industry. In addition, it was to provide the managers with jobs in the hospitality industry and create conditions for their free activities. On the other hand, due to his experience in banking and prudence in making strategic decisions, his good negotiation skills led to the rapid growth of the Hilton Hospitality industry chain.

For the first time in the history of the hospitality industry, Hilton organized meeting places, bars, newspapers and a souvenir shop. Also, the opening of such places is an additional source of income for the hospitality industry.

The main goal of the Hilton hospitality industry is to satisfy guests and ensure that their needs are met. The hotel industry chain name Hilton has all the features. So that; Hospitality; I am the Whole; L - Leadership; T - teamwork; O - Property; H - Now (Now - fast service). Hilton is the most famous brand in the hospitality industry. More than 530 hotels in 76 countries of the world; Conrad Hotels & Resorts - shows the country where it is located. It is a luxury hospitality industry featuring beautiful guest houses; Double Tree Hilton -

Services for Hilton HHonors Premium Program Guests gifts, luxury hotel; Home two suites by Hilton is a long-standing hospitality industry; "Hilton Rooms consist only of suites and luxury rooms. The Hilton brand has been operating since 1983. There are more than 200 such hospitality industries worldwide; "Hilton Garden Inn" - this hospitality industry organizes events such as seminars, meetings, conferences.

Homepton - distinguished in the hospitality industry by refunding the amount paid if the reason for customer dissatisfaction is valid. There are more than 1,800 of this type of hospitality industry worldwide;

Valdorf Astoria Hotels and resorts - built in the heart of nature. It is different from other hospitality institutions for its architectural style and services. Hilton Baku Hotel, which is part of the Hilton hospitality industry, is built in the center of Baku.

The luxury hotel, consisting of 308 rooms, also has a service level of 63 rooms. Loof Bar on the 25th floor of its own hospitality industry with a revolving floor, customers can enjoy breathtaking views. Hilton Baku plays a special role in the hospitality industry of Azerbaijan. Facilitates delivery to Baku in European and American style to work under the well-known Hilton brand.

In 1957, the Marriott hospitality industry chain was founded in Arlington, Virginia, United States, by John Hampillard Marriott. The rapidly growing hospitality industry network Marriott was established in 1981 and is opening the 100th hotel. With services such as resort hotels, cruise ships, the hospitality industry caters to the entertainment and needs of customers. Marriott currently manages about 20 brands, including six related to the hospitality industry. Marriott's main motto is full compliance with standards. For this reason, the examination of the leaders of the hospitality industry is the assessment of the quality of the work of the employees, the level of service (10, p. 78).

Every year, Marriott visits the hospitality industry auditor to determine. The Auditor acts as a guest, measures the level and fills out the appropriate forms. Evaluation is done with a 100-point system. If the rating is low and the situation is repeated several times, the brand of the hospitality industry is canceled. In addition, it compiles a "Staff Memory Book" to improve the level of service to personnel. What is written in this brochure is discussed by employees for 15 minutes every day. In this way, employees are motivated and engaged every day.

Marriott hospitality industry operates in 70 countries around the world. 2750 hotels of the network operate. As you can see, there are many world-famous brands of the hospitality industry in Azerbaijan, which should be noted for their invaluable role in the development of the hospitality industry in Azerbaijan.

Conclusion

The most dynamically developing service sector, which brings millions of dollars in revenue to the national economies of many countries, is the hotel business. Globalization processes have led to the intensification of the incorporation of hotels into groups or chains as a new form of economic organization with elements of cooperation and

integration. The creation and rapid expansion of World hotel chains is an objective process that will continue in the future. Hotel chains are based on a collective work system under the direct supervision of chain management. Members of the hotel chain are united by general norms, rules, standards, style, forms of management and business behavior.

The creation of hotel chains allows the enterprise to gain advantages over single enterprises: economies of scale; increasing investment opportunities; acquaintance with world brands; integration of reservation, provision and Information Systems; constant growth in the quality of Service. A study of the history of the emergence and development of hotel chains in the world showed that hotel chains appeared in Europe. Hotel chains have arisen as a result of the long evolution of the hospitality business. In the middle of the last century, two models for organizing hotel chains were developed.

The European model was the formation of hotel chains, where the main focus was refinement and aristocracy, and the main commercial form of chain organization was rental, leasing and franchising. American models of the organization of the hotel chain are based on uniform standards for all hotels, the flexibility of the organization system and the development of a single set of services. In general, the American model of hotel chains is more diverse and has strong historical "foundations" that allow American hotel chains to dominate the global market. The history of development of hotel chains in Russia is not rich. The beginning of the process is related to the arrival of large hotel chains to the Russian market in the early 90s. During this period, attempts to create a national hotel chain were unsuccessful. Foreign hotel chains also entered the Russian market very carefully and slowly.

An analysis of the current state and development trend of World hotel chains allowed us to draw the following conclusions: Europe is a leader in the development of the hospitality industry. Most hotels in the region are independent. However, the development of hotel chains is actively going on here. Europe is the most attractive market for most hotel companies. The development of hotel chains in Europe has been going through the acquisition of one hotel chain by another for a long time. The top ten includes three European hotel chains - InterContinental Hotels Group, Accor, Hilton Group plc., whereas the number of hotels and rooms in the networks is very different. The existing European chains are not very large, only 14 of them have more than 100 hotels in their portfolio.

World hotel chains covered almost all European countries, the most developed in this regard are Spain, Great Britain, Germany, France. America, above all North America, is the leader in the development of hotel chains, most of the region's hotels are included in hotel chains. More than half of the world's largest hotels are located in the United States. The largest of them are Cendant Corp., Marriott International, Choice Hotels International, Hilton Hotels Corp., Best Western International, Starwood Hotels & Resorts Worldwide, Hyatt Hotels / Hyatt International. The highest

concentrations of hotel chains in the Americas are in the United States, Canada, Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, the Caribbean and Central America. Most of Latin America does not have large national hotel chains. The hotel market is developing the fastest in Asia.

The main areas where the growth of the hospitality industry is concentrated are Asia - Southeast Asia, the Middle East and South Asia. World HOTEL chains aspire to the same areas. Asian hotel chains are still in the formative stage, they lag far behind European and American hotel chains in terms of key indicators. The most developed national hotel chains are in Japan and China, the rest of the countries are far behind. In Asia, the largest concentration of world hotel chains is located in Southeast Asia and the Middle East. African hotel chains are still in their infancy (6, p.89).

South Africa's national hotel chains have achieved some success, while other countries are dominated by foreign brands concentrated in South Africa, North Africa and the east coast of the continent. Unfortunately, the hotel business in our country has not reached the same scale as abroad due to many reasons, the study of economic and management fundamentals has not yet become a well-developed field of economics, and the management and marketing of hospitality services has not yet become a developed field. It has only recently begun to be taught at the university level.

Under these conditions, it is important to learn foreign experience as well as the local experience of using world trends in the development of the hospitality industry. For this reason, the study and use of foreign (world) experience remains relevant for Russia. The economic and political changes that have taken place in Russia over the past few years have revealed us the need to rethink and redefine the place and role of the hospitality industry. The importance and role of tourism for the development of the economy of the states, the satisfaction of individual needs, and the mutual enrichment of social relations between countries cannot be underestimated in Russia and the world today.

The activities of different branded hotels in Azerbaijan unite many cultures of the country. Criteria such as the introduction of American, Asian and European styles and the improvement of the level of hospitality service ensure the development of the industry. 64 management systems for well-known brands in the hospitality industry, staff organization, level of service, level of entertainment and leisure are reflected in the concluded contracts. Thus, companies with a well-known brand require compliance from the hospitality industry operating under the brand name in order to regulate the quality and meet the established standards.

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